

NUMERICAL STUDY OF DIFFUSION COMBUSTION OF METHANE IN AN AXISYMMETRIC TURBULENT JETS BASED ON MODEL PRANDTL.

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Annotation: In this article, a numerical method, algorithm, and numerical solutions are proposed for solving the problem of dispersion and diffusion combustion of methane in an axisymmetric flow of air in an infinite satellite flow. Dimensionless equations of the turbulent boundary layer of interacting gases were used to model the object. To solve the nonlinear differential equations of the system, a two-layer, four-point implicit finite difference scheme was used. Due to the non-linearity of the station storage and displacement equations, an iteration process was used. Due to the non-linearity of the differential equations of conservation of matter, internal (by speed) and external (by other indicators) iterative processes were established. In combustion processes, the rate of reaction of gas and air was taken to be very high, that is, they react as soon as they meet, and it was considered that diffusion burns. In this case, since the movement of the jet flow is a turbulent flow, the value of turbulence was found using the model of Prandtl. The results of calculating the temperature change along the flow axis are confirmed by experimental data. Separate results of numerical experiments are presented.

Keywords: turbulent jet, gas mixture, diffusion flame, temperature, velocity, total enthalpy, finite differences, computational experiment, mathematical model, implicit scheme, nonlinear equation, Mises variables, turbulent model, axis-symmetrical flow.

Currently, the majority of electricity in our country is obtained by turning gas. The need for energy throughout the world is growing due to a sharp increase in population every year. Energy shortages are one of the most important issues in the fuel and energy complex. Despite the improvement of gas suppliers, the beneficial work coefficients are improving now, noting more than 35 percent. Therefore, it is necessary to continue to further improve the work in this area. The problem of full burning of gas on gas suppliers is very important. As possible, the goal is to achieve the production of less harmful substances into the atmosphere. In daily life, the combination of the gas often is often seen in the pipe with a reaction with oxygen in the air.

It is necessary to take into account many factors related to the development of physico-chemical processes. Analytical methods for solving such problems do not exist yet, and experiments require a lot of money and research is considered complicated. Basically, in order to analyze combustion processes, we need to conduct more theoretical research, because there are not enough experimental devices in our country to study it experimentally. Therefore, the main way to study such processes is to build a numerical model of studying these processes and conduct a numerical experiment. Numerical simulation

allows obtaining information that cannot be obtained in laboratory experiments in many cases. That is why great importance is attached to numerical modeling of heat and mass exchange issues in the flow of multi-component reacting gases. When numerical simulation is used, it is possible to study process mechanisms taking into account changes in parameters. As a result of a sudden increase in temperature during combustion, complex physical processes occur. To analyze these processes, we need to model them mathematically. Here, it is convenient to use mathematical modeling methods, which are economically more effective than physical modeling. Large temperature and density gradients occur in heat exchange systems used in technical fields. Mathematical difficulties are encountered in the theoretical study of such physical processes. Such a process is solved using lineless differential equations to model the process. The difficulty side of addressing the problem is also here, as it is necessary to apply stable diagrams for equations, using the basic concepts of the mathematics to solve the linear differential equations.

There is also a physical complexity of the study of combustion processes. If we study the burning process, first of all, we look at the gas movement. Gases are usually always stuckly and irregularly moves. In the process of combustion,

due to the increase in temperature, the speed of movement increases and turbulence increases. The study of heat and metal issues is of great importance in the development of science and technology. The study of such issues is related to the need for thermal energy, chemical technology equipment [1-2].

Further theoretical methods were based on more accurate models of velocity and turbulent viscosity coefficients in the turbulent flow of liquids with constant physical properties in channels. In this case, it is necessary to use numerical methods in calculations.

A variety of flammable gases are used to obtain heat energy in the industrial oven. Currently, the decrease of gas reserves raises the issue of economical use of these gases. Also, if the gas is not completely burned, as a result of the burning of fuel, different amounts of toxic gases are released into the environment.

It is necessary to use the turbulent models to fully express this situation.

Until now, several [3] scientists have studied turbulent models and created new turbulent models. However, a universal model that fully represents the entire process has not yet been created. From this we can see that not all turbulent models give good results for the combustion process. Therefore, the study of turbulent flows does not yet have sufficient accuracy.

In this article, the turbulent was considered the final achievements of analyzing the flood reaction flows, where hydrogen fuels and the air is react to the limited velocity. Various models of turbulence have been used and theoretically analyzed for this problem. The process resulting from the reaction of gases was analyzed. Results have been obtained for different values of the Reynolds number. In this case, the results were obtained for laminar and turbulent motion and they were compared.

The concept of turbulence and its mathematical modeling.

As mentioned above, the system of differential equations for turbulent flows has not yet found its complete solution. Therefore, semi-empirical and adverse models are also used in engineering practice.

On the basis of such models issues related to the combination of Prandtl and lies on the fact that it is to find this accession. This is the coefficient of turbulent viscosity through this addition ν_T will be

connected. Such connections were first given by Prandtl for several open field flows. His research led to the theory that the turbulent flow mechanism depends on the averaged parameters of the flow. Based on Prandtl's confluence path hypothesis, turbulent motion is viewed as a fluid in a fluid volume, which maintains its speed and momentum of motion at some distance. Taking this into account, based on the measurement theory and the Bussinesk of hypothesis, it is possible to establish a reasonable connection between the test voltage and the connection path and the speed gradient. [4-6]:

$$\tau_{xy} \approx l^2 \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right| \frac{\partial u}{\partial y},$$

from this, it is possible to see the following relationship for the coefficient of kinematic turbulent viscosity;

$$\nu_T = l^2 \left| \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|,$$

Make a mathematical model of matter and choosing a mathematical model, putting on the border conditions.

We are given a horizontally placed pipe of radius a , something from him u_1 with velocity and T_1 let the flammable gas with temperature spread to the open area.

We assume that the wall of the pipe from which the gas is coming out is sufficiently smooth, that is, there are no bumps on the wall or any other obstacles that resist the movement of gas (Figure 1).

The combustion process has not yet started within the boundary of the current core. We define 2 limits in the current, the first is the combustion (torch) limit, the second is the flow limit, that is, the limit of the area reached by the flow movement.

Fig.1. Scheme of flow distribution to the open area.

In this case, the values of the longitudinal velocity up to the last sections of the pipe where

the gas is coming out will be the same. The static pressure considers the same to be the same and equal to atmospheric pressure: $P_1 = P_o = P_{atm}$

We enter the coordinates system as defined in the form. We place the coordinate head in the center of the small pipe and the section where the coordinate head is located, where the flammable gas exits from the pipe to the open area We define the horizontal bullet in the coordinate system with x, the vertical bullet y. The equations of boundary layer theory can be used to write a mathematical model of the problem [8]. In the boundary layer theory, the longitudinal velocity is assumed to be many times greater than the transverse velocity. Also, the pressure in the boundary layer does not change along the cross section, i.e. $\frac{\partial P}{\partial y} = 0$, the

pressure changes only along the longitudinal coordinate, in this case we write the considered process model using the equations of the boundary layer theory. Continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \cdot u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho \cdot v)}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Differential equation of motion

$$\rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\nu_t \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \quad (2)$$

Energy equation

$$\rho u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{y} \cdot \frac{1}{P_r} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho y \nu_t \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{P_r} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\rho y \nu_t \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{u^2}{2} \right) \right]$$

Concentration equation

$$\rho u \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Sc} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho \nu_t y \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) + w_i$$

Equation of state

$$P = T \rho R \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i}{m_i} \quad (3)$$

The total energy equation is also related to temperature T by the following algebraic equation:

$$H = C_p \cdot T + \frac{u^2}{2} + \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \cdot h_i^* \quad (4)$$

Here

$$C_p = \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \cdot C_{p_i}$$

We express the turbulent viscosity coefficient by the Prandtl formula:

$$\nu_t = \chi \cdot b(x) \cdot |U_{\max} - U_{\min}| \quad (5)$$

We select the boundary conditions for the above system of equations. In it, the x-coordinate is oriented horizontally, and the pipe is placed at the beginning of the coordinate. The coordinates believe that the head is placed in the pipe center and that the current is simplicated simmally to it, and there is no power from the side.

In this case, it is enough for us to see one side of the x-axis, because the parameters on the other side will be the same. Given these assumptions, the boundary conditions can be written in general as:

$$\begin{aligned} x=0: & 0 \leq y \leq a \\ & u = u_1, v = 0, \rho = \rho_1, H = H_1, C_i = C_i, \nu_t = \nu_1 \\ & 1 < y < y_\infty \\ & u = u_2, \vartheta = \vartheta_2, \rho = \rho_1, H = H_1, C_i = C_i, \nu_t = \nu_1 \\ x > 0: & y = 0 \\ & \left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \nu_t}{\partial y} = 0 \\ u \rightarrow u_2, H \rightarrow H_2, \vartheta \rightarrow 0, C_i \rightarrow C_i, y \rightarrow y_\infty \end{aligned} \right. \end{aligned}$$

Here, index 1 indicates the magnitudes of the components coming out of the pipe, and index 2 indicates the magnitudes of the satellite flow. One of the most common general methods of approximate solution of differential equations is the finite difference method. This method is also called the grid method when used in relation to the differential equation of the particular derivative.

There are two main directions for turbulence modeling. The first of them is the semi-empirical hypothesis of turbulence, and the second is the expression of turbulence through differential equations. Recently, there is an increase in the number of theoretical works written by expressing turbulence through differential equations [7-13], because the experimental results are also increasing.

Making equations dimensionless

We can transfer the given equations to dimensionless quantities.

$$\bar{u} = \frac{u}{u_1}, \bar{\vartheta} = \frac{\vartheta}{\vartheta_1}, \bar{H} = \frac{H}{H_1}, \bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_1}, \bar{x} = \frac{x}{a}, \bar{y} = \frac{y}{a}$$

We can transfer the given equations to dimensionless quantities.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial(\bar{x} \cdot a)} (\bar{\rho} \cdot \rho_1 \cdot \bar{u} \cdot u_1) + \frac{\partial}{\partial(\bar{y} \cdot a)} (\bar{\rho} \cdot \rho_1 \cdot \bar{\vartheta} \cdot u_1) = 0$$

If we remove the invariants from the above formula under the differential $\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u}) + \frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{\vartheta}) = 0$, both sides of the following equation $\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a}$.

If we divide to $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \cdot (\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{g}) = 0$, we

will have a view. Therefore, additional terms do not appear in the continuity equation when it is made dimensionless.

Now we make the differential equation of motion dimensionless using the equation. For this, we put the following appropriate values into the equation:

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{u}_1)}{\partial(\bar{x}a)} + \rho_1 \bar{v}_1 \frac{\partial(\bar{u}_1)}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} \left(\frac{\partial(\bar{u}_1)}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} \right) - \rho_1 \bar{g}$$

we remove the invariants from the equation under the differential:

$$\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1^2}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1^2}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{v} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} =$$

$$= \frac{u_1^2}{a} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \right) - \rho_1 \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot g$$

In the formula, both sides of the equation

$$\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1^2}{a}$$

will be divided into

$$\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{v} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \right) -$$

$$- \bar{\rho} \frac{a \cdot g}{u_1^2}$$

in the formula $\frac{u_1^2}{a \cdot g} = Fr$ - Given that the

$$\text{Frud number } \bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \bar{\rho} \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{\bar{\rho}}{Fr}$$

we get the equation.

We also make the energy equation dimensionless.

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{H}H_1)}{\partial(\bar{x} \cdot a)} + \rho_1 \bar{g} \frac{\partial(\bar{H}H_1)}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} =$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} \left(\bar{v}_1 u_1 a \frac{\partial(\bar{H} \cdot H_1)}{\partial(\bar{y} \cdot a)} \right)$$

we extract the invariants from under the differential:

$$\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1 \cdot H_1}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \cdot \frac{\partial(\bar{H})}{\partial x} + \frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1 \cdot H_1}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial y} =$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \cdot \frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1 \cdot H_1}{a} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial y} \right)$$

both sides of the equation $\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1 \cdot H_1}{a}$

$$\text{divided by: } \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial x} + \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{g} \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Pr} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{H}}{\partial y} \right),$$

The equation of state for gases is generally written as:

$$P = \rho \cdot R \cdot T \cdot \sum \frac{C_i}{m_i},$$

here C_i - contributions (concentration) of substances in one unit of air mass, they are dimensionless, all C_i for $\sum C_i = 1$. m_i - and the molar masses of these substances, $\frac{kg}{mol}$.

$\bar{P} = c \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{T} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i}{m_i}$ we will have. We P because we take it to be constant and equal to atmospheric pressure $P_1 = P_{atm}$ so $\bar{\rho} = \frac{c_1}{\bar{T} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i}{m_i}}$, As given in the

concentration equation, it has the following form:

$$\rho u \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Sc} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho v_{1y} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) + w_i$$

Here C_i - mass concentration of components in gas movement, w_i - in gas motion i -th the speed of formation of the component, $\frac{kg}{m^3 \cdot c}$.

Putting the quantities in the formula into the equation, we get the following:

$$\bar{\rho} \bar{u} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial(\bar{x} \cdot a)} + \bar{\rho} \bar{v} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} =$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial(\bar{y}a)} \left(\bar{\rho} \bar{v}_1 u_1 a \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial(\bar{y} \cdot a)} \right) + w_i$$

in the equation, we subtract the constants from the differential:

$$\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \frac{\partial(C_i)}{\partial x} + \frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a} \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{g} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} =$$

$$\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) + w_i$$

both sides of the equation $\frac{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}{a}$ divided

by:

$$\bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{u} \frac{\partial(C_i)}{\partial x} + \bar{\rho} \cdot \bar{g} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\bar{v}_1 \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) +$$

$$+ \frac{a}{\rho_1 \cdot u_1} w_i$$

$\frac{a}{\rho_1 \cdot u_1}$ we calculate the terms by setting the units of measurement:

We write the full energy equation in the equation:

$$H = C_p \cdot T + \frac{u^2}{2} + \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \cdot h_i^*,$$

Here H – full energy - measure $kkal/kg$, C_p - at constant pressure mixed heat capacity $kkal/(kg \cdot grad)$, h_i^* - i -th heat of component formation $kkal/kg$.

Now we will write all the equations converted to the dimensionless form in one place in the system, and for the sake of simplicity, we will remove dashes on them:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial(\rho \cdot u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho \cdot v)}{\partial y} = 0, \\ \rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(v_t \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{\rho}{Fr}, \\ \rho u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{y} \frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho y v_t \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{Pr} \right), \\ \frac{1}{y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\rho y v_t \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{u^2}{2} \right) \right], \\ \rho u \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Sc} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho \cdot v_t \cdot y \cdot \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{a}{\rho_1 \cdot u_1} w_i, \\ P = T \cdot \rho \cdot R \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i}{m_i}. \end{cases}$$

Now we make the equation dimensionless with boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0: & 0 \leq y \leq a \\ u = 1, v = 0, \rho = 1, H = 1, C_i = C_{i2}, v_t = v_2 \\ & 1 < y < y_\infty \\ u = \frac{u_1}{u_1}, \vartheta = \frac{\vartheta_1}{\vartheta_2}, \rho = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2}, H = \frac{H_1}{H_2}, C_i = C_{i1}, v_t = v_{t1} \\ x > 0: \\ y = 0: & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial y} = 0, \\ y \rightarrow y_\infty: & u \rightarrow \frac{u_1}{u_2}, H \rightarrow \frac{H_1}{H_2}, \vartheta \rightarrow 0, C_i \rightarrow C_{i1}, \end{aligned}$$

Fig.2 $T_1 = 600K$, $T_2 = 300K$ area of isotherms in methane diffusion combustion

Fig.3 $\bar{x} = 10$ va $\bar{x} = 180$ in sections concentration graph

Fig.4 Reagents and combustion products mass concentration curves $\bar{x} = 8$

Fig.5 Dimensionless along the axis of velocity change in value $T_1 = 297K$ $T_2 = 600K$ $u_2 = 61 m/s$.

According to calculations, fuel ignites as the temperature of the gas increases length decreases and temperature increases. An increase in air temperature is a flame leads to prolongation. In particular, $T_1 = 600K$, $T_2 = 300K$ maximum temperature $T^* = 3078.43K$ flame length $224.9a$ to equal (2-rasm) it was determined to be.

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